

Green Infrastructure Management Policies in Tunisia in Face of Climate Change

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Abstract

Green infrastructure (GI) is increasingly at the forefront of climate-resilient urban development with multifunctional benefits incorporated into urban ecological processes, social wellbeing, and sustainability. Global research indicates that GI contributes to climate adaptation by helping to regulate urban heat, manage stormwater, enhance biodiversity, and support healthier and more equitable living conditions. In arid and semi-arid contexts, particularly in the southern Mediterranean, however, planning green infrastructure is complicated by the effects of water constraints, weak governance modalities, and low institutional capacity. This review critically assesses green infrastructure management policies in Tunisia, one of the countries that is sharply exposed to climate risks, while also facing high rates of urbanization and ecological decline. The paper collates contemporary scientific outputs, national environmental strategies, and regional adaptation plans to assess the degree to which GI is recognized in climate policies and urban planning instruments. There is evidence that Tunisia acknowledged the strategic importance of GI in the national adaptation strategy, yet implementation is inconsistent and fragmented as there are significant challenges associated with resources, capacity, and support for the long-term maintenance of green infrastructure. Insights from comparable Mediterranean contexts provide information about commonalities but also suggest new opportunities through nature-based solutions, community-led initiatives, and water-efficient landscape models. To improve urban resilience and advance Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the research concludes with a list of top initiatives to improve GI governance in Tunisia. These include integrated planning, cross-sector collaboration, and climate-responsive landscape management.

Keywords: *Green infrastructure governance, Urban planning, Nature-based solutions, Climate policy, North Africa.*

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Introduction

Green infrastructure (GI) is defined as complex networks of natural, semi-natural, and engineered vegetated systems and has received considerable attention as an important element of urban climate resilience. Climate change (CC) is a serious phenomenon that has gained significant worldwide attention in recent times, particularly in developing countries that are heavily impacted by its effects (Adham et al. 2019). The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change describes CC as “*a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods*”. According to several climate models, CC will increase the frequency and severity of droughts, which will reduce the amount of water available (Li et al. 2018), especially in arid and semi-arid areas worldwide. A recent systematic review pointed to GI's ability to regulate urban temperatures, reduce flood risk, and provide regulating ecosystem services; GI, thus, is a potent nature-based solution to climate hazards (Salih et Nagy 2024). A climate crisis is intensifying heatwaves, drought, and coastal threat risks in Mediterranean cities, even in North Africa, and the consequences of urbanization add to these vulnerabilities (Portner et al. 2022; Nastos et Saaroni 2024). Yet still the deployment of blue-green infrastructure in the region is uneven.

In Tunisia, climate-related risks are being exacerbated by water scarcity, coastal erosion, and governance issues. The World Bank universe was reported to threaten significant adverse impacts to both infrastructure and livelihoods from rising sea levels and increased variability in precipitation (World Bank Group, 2023). Reports from within Tunisia also find only limited municipalities take action on adaptation, with limited capacity from democratic decentralized systems, centralized governing structures and lack of local resources to undertake action (Yerkes & Arkeh, 2024). Tunisia has currently adopted a transitional low-carbon strategy nationally, however, operationalizing GI into urban planning has been more incomplete and increasingly patchy (Sabry, 2025). Participation justice also remains under considered and explored as a potential supporting source of climate resilience; recent work on climate activism within Tunisia suggest that civil society can play a central role within questions of adaptation policy (El Amine, 2025).

Thus, this review seeks to synthesize and critically assess the state of green infrastructure policy and governance in Tunisia, in relation to the Mediterranean global context. Through empirical studies, policy documents, and regional reviews we will identify the key challenges and opportunities to enhance GI in Tunisian cities and provide useful recommendations to couple urban planning, climate adaptation, and sustainable development.

Green Infrastructure Theory

The emergence of the GI concept aims to enhance urban green space networks by considering them as a unified planning entity (Sandstrom, 2002). It includes natural and semi-natural spaces such as parks, gardens, squares, farmland, green belts, etc. (Sutton-Grier et al. 2015). The concept of GI emphasizes the quality as well as quantity of urban and peri-urban green spaces (Ajmi et al. 2023a, Turner, 1995). It is notable that, beyond the narrow definition of a “green space”, this concept is based on a fundamental connection and the ability to provide highly valued ecological and pastoral spaces in both urban and rural areas (Boussema et al. 2024). Historically, it was developed as an outcome of the projects undertaken by

landscape architects Frederick Law Olmsted (1822-1903) and Jean-Claude Nicolas Forestier (1861-1930) to enhance the quality of life in major 19th-century cities such as New York, Paris, and London. Through their work, a network of urban green areas was established, enhancing both the general well-being of citizens and the operational efficiency of cities (Bel Fekih Boussema et al. 2022). Furthermore, Ebenezer Howard (1850–1928), is recognized for proposing a new urban model represented by a large city made up of “Garden cities” interconnected. In the middle of these cities, there is a large natural park encircled by residential areas. Originally, the concept had an artistic vision, then it gradually evolved into an ecological vision and, later, became a tool for sustainable spatial planning and territorial governance (Bousemma et al. 2018).

According to Lapierre & Pellerin (2018), GI can be classified into four main categories: urban canopy (Figure 1), green open spaces (Figure 2), green roofs (Figure 3), and vertical greenery systems such as facades and walls (Figure 4). The urban canopy is the extent of plant cover in a specific area. It is essentially the trees and shrubs of green streets and alleys, as well as the urban forest (Bartesaghi Koc et al. 2017). Green belts, green corridors, urban public open spaces, urban plant structures, urban parks, vegetated ground cover, and protected spaces are the main components of green open spaces (Simard et al. 2019).

Figure 1. Urban canopy in Sidi Yahya Garden, Sousse (Tunisia)
Source: Ajmi et al. 2023

Figure 2. Open public garden, Sousse (Tunisia)
Source: @Ajmi, 2024

Figure 3. Green roof in Canada (credit photo: Javier Frutos)
Source: <https://blog.denbow.com/>

Figure 4. One Central Park wall, Sydney
Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/>

According to Tzoulas et al. (2007), a GI's features and components may support ecosystem health in a number of ways. Urban and peri-urban areas contribute to the preservation of biodiversity variety by increasing the diversity of natural, semi-natural, and artificial vegetation (Flores et al. 1998). Moreover, it plays an essential role in climate change adaptation (Geneletti et Zardo 2016; Takács et al. 2016), enhancing rainwater management capacity (Pappalardo et al. 2017; Raci et al. 2019), reducing heat island impact (Saaroni et al. 2018; Wang et Banzhaf 2018), and decreasing environmental pollution (Livesley et al. 2016). If a GI is proactively planned, developed, and maintained it has the potential to guide urban development by providing a framework for economic growth and nature conservation (Walmsley 2006; Schrijnen 2000). It enables i) improving the quality of life for populations and citizens by establishing a safe and healthy environment; ii) conserving biodiversity by limiting and minimizing the fragmentation of natural environments and reliant areas by facilitating local wildlife migrations; and iii) preserving against the vulnerability of climate change, such as soil erosion, carbon storage, inundations, and flooding (Boussema et al. 2024).

Green Infrastructure Methods and Design

GI is an ecological network, a set of ecosystems linked together by flows of organisms in a spatially coherent whole, interacting with the landscape matrix (Opdam et al., 2006). Moreover, conceptualizing such a network is essentially based on identifying ecological reservoirs and corridors. According to Sordello et al. (2017) and following the diversity of methods observed and criteria used to define and map biodiversity reservoirs and corridors, it results in a strong heterogeneity of GI, which is linked to the methodological choice adopted.

Identification of Biodiversity Reservoirs

The identification of biodiversity reservoirs can be divided into two main types, namely 'primary' and 'secondary' nuclei. According to Linglart et al. (2016), primary nuclei constitute spaces either of significant size or subject to a protection scheme (regulatory environments) where species can carry out their entire life cycle. The larger these spaces are, the more they accommodate different habitats and many species. They are generally the main sources of species for a large part of the neighbouring territories (Liénard & Clergeau, 2011). The secondary nuclei have a smaller area and consist of less qualitative habitats hosting species that can complete part of their life cycle (Locquet & Clauzel, 2018). There is also another type of reservoir designated as "other habitats"; these are the habitats that may be home to certain species, but they are of lesser importance. According to Amsallem et al. (2018), multiple methods are employed for the identification of biodiversity reservoirs from inventory zonings and regulatory zones, a species entry, or a natural habitats entry.

Inventory Zoning and Regulatory Areas

According to Amsallem et al. (2010), these are management or preservation areas such as Natural Zones of Ecological Interest, Fauna and Flora, National Nature Reserves, the hearts of National Parks, classified and registered sites (Natura 2000 sites and Ramsar sites), the Prefectural Biotope Protection Stops, and Sensitive Natural Spaces. However, these zonings make it possible to articulate the different nature protection policies and to know the ecological interest of the site, which will be integrated into the desired ecological network. The identification of these zonings mainly represents the first step in the work of collecting them. Dehouck & Amsallem (2017) have distinguished cases where all Natura 2000 habitats are integrated, whereas others first analyze the evolution and quality of habitats within these sites while considering that these environments may have evolved since their classification. Thus, there is a strong heterogeneity between the methods used to take these zonings into account (Amsallem et al., 2010). Furthermore, this approach has been tested by Bernier & Théau (2013), who concluded that it offers little flexibility since it is determined in advance by the location and configuration of protected areas,

which do not necessarily provide the best habitat. In addition, if the study area includes small protected areas, this does not allow for the tracing of corridors.

Method of Input Species

Bergès et al. (2010) and Fu et al. (2010) stated that it is a method based on the ecological requirements of the studied species and their movement capacities associated with the ecological quality of the environments. The first objective is to identify the spatial relationships between the vital domains specific to a species (Foltête et al., 2012; Bourgeois et al., 2017). For this method, data on species are used for their intrinsic conservation values, and a distinction is made between emblematic, heritage, remarkable, or even threatened species.

However, certain species of national consistency or decisiveness for GI can be identified from where some countries have developed a list of species representative of the environments considered for GI such as France and Switzerland. So, the identification of these species and their distributions indicate the presence of sites of strong ecological interest, and since then they are the ones who will present the reservoirs of biodiversity.

However, the consideration of species is very variable according to the experiments; it essentially depends on the availability of naturalistic data. Some rely on data for a few species, and others consider an entire list. It is then possible to work on groups of species not too rare, and characteristic of the types of habitats given; we then speak of a species guild, and in terms of data, these come from multiple sources: naturalistic associations, botanical conservatories, conservatories of natural areas, departmental fishing federations, etc. (Amsallem et al., 2010).

Method of input Habitat

Locquet and Clauzel (2018) indicated that it is a structural approach since it focuses mainly on environments rather than species and the physical links between elements, as highlighted by Bergès et al. (2010). It consists of identifying all the natural habitats of the territory or a habitat of a particular species (target species). As stated by Sordello et al. (2017), the boundary between the medium method and the natural habitats method can sometimes be blurred. The best-quality settings for the chosen target species are chosen as nodal zones, as Bernier & Théau (2013) emphasized in the same context.

Identification of Biodiversity Corridors

Corridors are linear areas of land, strips of land, or vegetation that differ from the surrounding landscape matrix (Forman & Godron, 1986; Barrett & Bohlen, 1991). They are useful for the dispersal of organisms in landscapes (Inglis & Underwood, 1992) as they structurally connect two habitat cores (Kindlmann & Burel, 2008). Different methods are used to identify corridors by applying visual analysis or applying geomatics tools.

Visual Interpretation Method

Ecological continuities are identified by photointerpretation from aerial photographs and/or land use maps. This method consists of defining and manually tracing the most direct path separating two discontinuous natural spaces by modulating the path layout according to land use (Spaggiari et al., 2010; Sordello et al., 2017).

Dilatation-Erosion Method

The processing is done in two steps and applies to all the habitat tasks of each of the sub-frames. For the dilation, it is a question of expanding these tasks by a buffer zone of width corresponding to the estimated dispersal distance of the target species. This expansion allows certain close tasks to come into contact and merge, which causes the creation of a 'potential corridor' (Amsallem et al., 2010); which makes it possible to distinguish potentially well-connected areas from poorly or non-connected ones. However,

as for erosion, it is a matter of retreating to a width identical to expansion; thus, potential connection areas between tasks appear, and all areas of the expansion halo that did not allow merging two tasks will be removed (Spaggiari et al., 2010).

Permeability of Media Method

The method is based on a calculation under Geographic Information System (GIS) using a "distance-cost" propagation-diffusion function (Berthoud et al., 2004). It takes into account the movement capacities of species that vary depending on the habitat crossed. Depending on the species considered, land use is then considered more or less permeable to the movement of these species. The calculation makes it possible to distinguish different areas according to their degree of permeability and to define the potential area of movement of the target species, called continuum (Amsallem et al., 2010).

Graph Theory Method

According to Foltête et al. (2012), the work of Bunn et al. (2000) and Urban & Keitt (2001), are among the first who used graph theory methods to characterize ecological networks. A few years later, several authors have contributed to adapting the generic framework of graph theory to the ecological and geographical specificities of these networks (Saura & Pascual-Hortal, 2007; Urban et al., 2009; Dale & Fortin, 2010). Furthermore, this theory allows for the ranking of ecological reservoirs and corridors according to their importance within the identified ecological network, based on their position in the landscape or their surface area (Dehouck & Amsallem, 2017).

In this same context, Locquet & Clauzel (2018) explained that it is a matter of identifying the accessibility of all the elements of the landscape matrix about the movement capacities of the considered species. Avon & Bergès (2014) pointed out that many indices can be calculated at different levels, such as the landscape, to measure the overall network connectivity, or at the task level to count connectivity on a smaller scale. However, various measurement tools exist, such as the least cost path, the least cost corridor, or circuit theory.

The methods presented for identifying reservoirs or corridors are neither exhaustive nor exclusive and may be interdependent or nested. Table 1 presents a summary of the different works consulted, summarizing the method(s) used in each case study. To conclude, in different countries of the world, the methods applied to the development of GI can be grouped into five: field surveys, remote sensing, GIS, landscape metrics, and graph theory. We notice that in most cases GIS are always present, and they are combined with other methods. Recognize that the selection of a method is frequently heavily influenced by the availability of basic information, its representativeness, and homogeneity. Thus, we are discussing a cross-section of methodologies.

Table 1. Literature Review of the Different Methodological Approaches Used in Some Research Works for the Development of GI

Author, Year, Country	Field surveys	Remote sensing	GIS	Landscape metrics	Graph theory
Miller et al., 1998, Prescott Valley-USA			X		
Venturelli & Galli, 2006, Italy			X	X	
Taylor et al., 2007, Genesee Country-USA		X	X	X	
Giordano & Riebel, 2008, Sao Paulo-Brazil			X	X	
Wiens et al., 2009, Florida-USA	X		X		
Pena et al., 2010, Lisbonne-Portugal		X	X		
Mahmoud & El-Sayed, 2011, El-Sadat-Egypt				X	
Borre et al., 2011, Member States of the European Union	X	X	X		
Consalés et al., 2012, Marseille-France			X	X	

Chang et al., 2012, Shenzhen-China			X	X	X
Bernier & Théau, 2013, Québec-Canada			X	X	X
Maire et al., 2014, Gers-France				X	
Linglart et al., 2016, Plaine commune-France		X	X		
Locquet & Clauzel, 2018, Ardennes-France			X		X
Clauzel & Bonneville, 2019, France			X		X
Boussema et al., 2022, Sousse-Tunisia	X	X	X		
Kosma et al., 2023, Jyväskylä-Finland					X
Qui et al., 2025, Jiangsu, China		X			X
Boussema et al., 2025, Kerkennah-Tunisia		X			X

To summarize, the methods addressed using geomatic treatments under GIS are methods that belong to "exact science" since they rely on equations and calculated indices; they are automatic treatments applicable at any scale, whereas the visual interpretation method is sometimes considered difficult to apply in view of the working scale and the large surface area of the regions to be studied. The identification of a potential, functional and sustainable GI for a territory requires its intersection with spatial planning projects. It is indeed a question of integrating GI into the overall territorial project or even constituting one of the pillars of the sustainable spatial planning project. Subsequently, a shared GI results from a consensus between ecological issues and development issues.

Green Infrastructure Management Strategies in Tunisia

GI provides numerous environmental benefits (Redon, 2017), by minimizing the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs) that contribute significantly to current climate change (Nowak et Crane, 2002). In addition to its role in sequestering pollutants, soundproofing and providing shade, GI can play a key role in combating heat islands (Pauleit et Duhme, 2000 ; Abo Elata, 2017 ; Aram et al., 2019 ; Zhou et al., 2019 ; Masoudi et al., 2021). Moreover, the introduction of vegetation into urban environments can be extremely effective in reducing stress factors, particularly those related to higher temperatures (Grahn et al., 2003 ; Charfi et al., 2014 ; Sugawara et al., 2021 ; Le Mentec, 2022). According to Gill et al. (2007), the advantages of GI extend far beyond amenity considerations, and during periods of drought, developing adaptable techniques is urgently needed to be made from regional spatial strategies to local development frameworks to development control inside urban neighborhoods to minimize the effects of change climate, especially in developing countries like Tunisia which is situated in the Maghreb region of North Africa.

A phenomenon of rural migration emerged after Tunisia got independence in 1956, mostly due to the agricultural crises of the 1930s and the port cities' economic growth that attracted the improve rished from the countryside (Sethom, 1992). As a result, there was an imbalance in the socio-spatial use of green space, most of which was urbanized. Furthermore, the boundaries of agricultural land have continued to be pushed back by the growth of Tunisia's towns (Ajmi Ismail, 2023). Since then, the ecological and social significance of green areas, as well as their adequate quantity and distribution across the city, have been increasingly apparent to public authorities (Fahem, 2021). The rise of interest in green spaces and activities is shown by the establishment of the Green Plan in Tunis in 1977, which defined standards in the form of percentages of green space per person and added a "green space" component to urban planning (Bousemma et al. 2018).

Since independence, a few environmental protection-related codes and regulations have been passed, including the Land Use and Urban Planning Code (CATU), the forestry code established in 1966 and updated in 1988, the water code made in 1975, and the 1986 legislation on cultural property (Loukil, 2012). Among these laws, the CATU, which was enacted in 1994 to replace the 1979 city planning code, is the primary one that currently governs land use and urban planning in Tunisia, namely the development

of urban green spaces (Girard, 2006). Furthermore, as mentioned in Article 12 of the CATU, "Urban Development Plans (PAU) determine [...] the exact positions reserved for structures, community facilities, public utility facilities, green spaces, and public squares, in accordance with an equipment grid established by decree, and set out land use rules and easements". Infrastructure master plans, mobility master plans, public space master plans, economic and social development plans, and urban development plans are the primary instruments used in land-use planning. PAU serves to highlight pre-existing elements within the city so that they can then be connected together to create a network or green grid (Fatmi et al. 2015). It prohibits and regulates changes in the use of green spaces. Only a presidential decree can modify these functions. In practice, all green spaces in cities are either planned and built on the basis of the PAU, or integrated into these documents during the revision process for those planned and built after PAU approval, or as part of subdivision operations. However, it should be emphasized that not all the green spaces provided for in PAUs are actually created, since the area in question has not yet been developed (Turki & Zaâfrane Zhioua, 2006).

The 1970s saw the emergence of new organizations as well, and up until the early 1980s, governmental agencies dominated Tunisia's building industry. These included the 1973-founded Industrial Land Agency, the Tourist Land Agency, and Housing Land Agency. These organizations are in charge of governing land use and urban development in the residential, commercial, and tourism sectors. Additionally, They are also responsible for land acquiring, developing and disposing for green spaces and construction, for residential use or for building industrial or tourist units (Abbès Belghith, 2017). Green areas in PAU can be developed (UVa), equipped (UVb), natural (UVd), or cemeteries (UVe). In contrast to UVb, which are defined as « green areas for sports, leisure activities, playgrounds or amusement parks and demountable buildings» (Figure 5). UVa are defined as "existing or to-be-created green areas such as public gardens, squares, parks, crossroads, etc. ». Regarding UVd, « all urbanization is prohibited in these natural green zones». UVe are « areas reserved for existing or planned cemeteries. They must be landscaped with green spaces, the main paths and the perimeter bordered by trees » (Abdelkafi et Mezgar, 2007).

Figure 5. Urban Development Plans of Sousse municipality, Tunisia
Source: <https://sousse.maps.arcgis.com/apps/>

More specifically, the planning of these different types of green spaces is based on an urban planning approach with various urban planning documents, and on a project-based approach with specific plans for the development of green spaces (Turki & Zaâfrane Zhioua, 2006). « A green area that has been designated as such through a development plan may only lose it by decree issued on the suggestion of the Minister in charge of Urban Planning, following agreement with the Minister in charge of the Environment and Regional Planning », according to Article 2011 of the CATU. This article demonstrates the government's interest in green spaces, which are hard to devalue (Ajmi Ismail, 2023). Furthermore, the boundary for the establishment of green spaces is shown by the PAU's green space grid. A square, for instance, is made for at least 20 residences, with a 1.5 m² threshold for each occupant. Depending on the density of the city's infrastructure, a garden with a threshold of 2.5 to 3 m² per resident is given for at least 10,000 dwellings. There are at least three hectares of urban parks available for more than 50,000 people. The grid shows not just the ratios of green space to population, but also the best places for green spaces: near elementary schools and on the edges of cities (Loukil, 2012). In fact, any urban green space that exists is either reincorporated into these papers throughout revisions or is planned and executed as part of the Urban Plan. The National Urban Parks Program, which was started in the early 1990s to shape a "green policy" aimed at creating about a hundred parks throughout Tunisia, and the Urban Gardens Program, two other programs created by the Ministry of the Environment, are examples of initiatives that are used to carry out green space planning. Another initiative funded by the National Environment Protection Agency (ANPE) is the National Project for Cleanliness and Environmental Aesthetics, which designates municipalities that fulfill specific requirements as "garden cities." (Bousemma et al. 2018). Chapter II of the CATU, under "Land use conditions," discusses the many types of urban planting. The creation or extension of industrial installations and buildings, light or temporary constructions, may be governed by specific circumstances, such as the creation of green screens or the observation of a setback, according to article 912, which also mentions "green screens," a form intended to embellish exterior constructions. Article 1113 of the same chapter mentions other forms as well, such as "roadside plantings," which "must be laid out and maintained in such a way as not to hinder traffic and visibility at crossroads and bends, and not to hinder the improvement and enhancement of urban and natural landscapes," and "spaces reserved for planting," which "must, unless otherwise required, be at least 50% planted." This article explains the several types of public planting programs that are available and stresses the value of maintaining plantings to improve a city's landscape (Ajmi Ismail, 2023).

Beyond these general regulations and laws, there are significant differences in Tunisia's creation, maintenance, and management of these green areas. An analysis of the locations of public parks and gardens in northeastern Tunisia revealed that while working-class neighborhoods, where socioeconomic conditions are more challenging, have little to no public green space, wealthy neighborhoods especially those in the tourist zone often have well-kept and supervised public green spaces. This is because public and private companies are involved in the mixed management structure. However, in wealthy neighborhoods and metropolitan areas, green spaces administration is mostly mixed, with private businesses handling maintenance (Loukil et al. 2012).

However, most municipalities in Tunisia, mainly use the direct administration system where urban green spaces are managed by the green spaces department within the municipality (Ajmi et al. 2023). On the other hand, public parks and gardens are generally managed by the Ministry of the Interior in Tunisia (86%), but most of them (66%) are managed directly by local authorities. Some green spaces are under the supervision of the Ministry of the Environment, but very few (20% of mixed management) are under mixed management with private companies. Some municipalities also monitor green spaces development projects to some extent, subcontracting management to private companies. 12% of Tunisia's parks and gardens are under this indirect management system. In this instance, businesses oversee preservation, but the area is still open to the public during business hours (Ajmi Ismail, 2023). Municipalities frequently assign private persons or businesses to run amenities like snack spaces, mini zoos, playgrounds, sports

fields, and kiosks. The area around these features, like Ibn Eljazzar Park in the municipality of Sousse (Figure 6), is then still under the private investor's authority (Zhioua, 2002). Other parks are under direct government supervision, managed by the ANPE (2%), which is supervised by the Ministry of the Environment. One of the main reasons for the poor quality of green spaces and the resulting inconvenience is the lack of budget for their maintenance (Fahem, 2022) and vandalism by local residents, according to many local authority representatives (Ajmi et al. 2023).

For example, in a square in Sousse, two trees were cut down at night by a resident in the nearby neighborhood (Figure 7). The director of the sub-directorate for green spaces at the municipality of Sousse mentioned that « *This is due to complaints made by residents in the surrounding neighborhoods...bad company and uncivil practices, particularly those of couples in this space, have been reported several times I think this is the main reason why this man cut down the trees...* » (Ajmi Ismail , 2023).

Figure 6. Ibn Eljazzar park entrance, Municipality of Sousse (2024)
Source: @Ajmi, 2024

Figure 7. Vandalism in the Square Avenue Yesser Arafet, Municipality of Sousse (2023)
Source: <https://www.jawharafm.net/ar/article>

Conclusion

The review indicates that GI is central to urban climate resilience, providing ecological, social, and economic benefits beyond grey infrastructure. Tunisia has made progress in recognizing nature-based solutions of strategic importance to the nation, but there are still substantial deficits in governance coherence, long-term funding, and local technical capacity. National and municipal policy strengthening

requires a transition to integrated multi-scalars of planning that includes GI in climate adaptation planning, land-use planning, and water management. Tunisia's experience is a broader reflection of challenges in many southern Mediterranean and MENA cities, where rapid urbanization, water scarcity, and ecosystem degradation increase climate risk. Thus, effective GI governance in the region has implications for urban resilience, but also for biodiversity, public health, social equity, and progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) notably, SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities) and SDG 13 (Climate Action). Working with locally adapted vegetation, community-based stewardship of GI, and innovative irrigation technologies will help bridge the gap between policy intent and implementation on the ground.

In conclusion, promoting GI in Tunisia and other arid urban contexts requires a long-term vision underpinned by cross-sector collaboration, scientific monitoring, and inclusive decision-making processes. This approach will be central to establishing climate-responsive, socially inclusive, and ecologically functional cities that are better able to deal with the intensified impacts of CC.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

Abbreviations

ANPE: National Environment Protection Agency

CATU: Land Use and Urban Planning Code

GI: Green Infrastructure

GIS: Geographic Information System

PAU: Urban Development Plans

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